

PERFORMANCE OF WATER RESOURCES INFORMATION SYSTEM MANAGEMENT OF CISADANE WATERSHED, BANTEN PROVINCE

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ABSTRACT

The introduction of information systems is an improvement in the conservation of water resources in Indonesia today in reality it is still not optimally utilized by the community where water resources are a need that cannot be released in improving the welfare of human life, in this sector the government has an important role in efforts to change The behavior of the community in receiving information on the water resource management system where the water resource information management system is unavoidable and very much required for the general public in everyday life and this can have an impact on organizational performance if this information cannot reach the community specifically water users . Government steps have also been taken to support and encourage the acceleration of the water resource information system through the management of the water resource information system, including by increasing the development of a water source information management system through the scope of work in the Cidurian-Cisadane Watershed Management work unit in the Banten Province area which based on administrative authority is limited by the authority of the Ministry Public Works and Public Housing delegated by the Ciliwung-Cisadane Center. However, in addition to building a water resources information system, the government's challenges to develop human resources. If this can be done quickly and on target to water users, then all water problems in Indonesia can have an important role in the life cycle of water resource infrastructure.

Keywords: Performance, Information systems, Sumber daya water, Watersheds

INTRODUCTION

Water is a source of life that cannot be replaced by anything. Without water then people, animals and plants would not be able to live. Conservation of water resources is an effort to maintain the existence, sustainability, state, nature and function of water resources so that they are always available in sufficient quantity and quality to meet the needs of living things both at present and in the generations that are about to come.

Water is included in the hydrological cycle. Hydrology comes from the Greek, Hydrologic, which means "water science". Hydrology is a branch of Geography that studies the movement, distribution, and quality of water throughout the Earth, including the hydrological cycle and water resources. People who are experts in the field of hydrology are called hydrologists, work in the fields of earth sciences and environmental sciences, as well as civil engineering and environmental engineering. Hydrology is the science that studies water in all its forms (liquids, solids and gases), located insider above the surface of the soil including among others the spread of its cycle and behavior, physical and chemical properties, and its relationship with living elements in water itself. Hydrology also studies rain behavior mainly covering periods

of rainfall re-occurrence as it relates to flood calculations as well as plans for each civil engineering building including weir, dams and bridges.

Conservation of water resources is an effort to maintain the existence, sustainability of the state of nature, and function of water resources so that they are always available in sufficient quantity and quality to meet the needs of living things both now and in future generations. Utilization of water resources is an effort to manage, provide, use, develop, and manage water resources optimally, successfully and efficiently. Control and control of water damage is an effort to prevent and overcome the occurrence of environmental damage caused by water damage which can be in the form of floods, cold lava, omtubs, tidal waves and others.

Management is an effort to plan, implement, monitor, and evaluate the implementation of conservation, utilization of water resources, and control of water damage. Water resource stewardship is an effort to determine the zone of utilization of water sources and the allocation of water to water sources. The provision of water resources is an effort to meet the need for water and water power to meet various needs with appropriate quality and quantity. The use of water resources is the use of water resources and their infrastructure as media and / or materials. Water resource development is an effort to increase the usefulness of the function of water resources without damaging the environmental balance. In water resource management, there are performance benchmarks, namely:

1. Collection and processing of hydrological data
2. Flood and drought monitoring
3. Management of surface water use data
4. Survey and investigation of hydrological post buildings, maintenance of hydrological facilities and infrastructure.

Water resource development and management programs for the collection and processing of hydrological data that become the benchmark of performance, namely:

- A. Rainfall data collection. Rainfall data is nothing more than a record of the amount of daily rainfall at a particular location or area, most of which data is obtained manually by measuring the amount of rainwater collected on the rainfall measuring device on that day. The data is then collected every day and reported regularly to institutions that deal with climate and weather, namely the Meteorology, Climatology and Geophysics Agency (BMKG) to be then analyzed and used as a reference for climate and weather information.

The rainfall that has been collected and analyzed at the BMKG will be a reference for the preparation of climate and weather forecasts that are completed by almost all sectors, determination of the calendar year an, disaster mitigation, and preparation of infrastructure development plans and needed for supporting data on various research activities. That is why, until now, rainfall records are very important because they can contribute to experts for various analyses of the rainfall, even as evidence that the rainfall has always remained in volume in the same place throughout the world. Jadi,

who has been considered the cause of the rain is considered to be the cause of the flood is very wrong because the rainfall is fixed.

Rainfall data collection is carried out at 12 (twelve) rainfall post points spread over the working area, namely in the area:

Table 1. Location of rainfall posts

Kabupaten/Kota	No. Urut	Kode / Nomor	Nama Pos Hujan	KOORDINAT
1	2	3	4	5
Kota Tangerang	1	30 I	Pasar Baru	LS 6° 9'33.47" BT 106°37'42.22"
Kab. Tangerang	2	34 C	Serpong	LS 06 18' 43.17" BT 106 39' 28.48"
Kab. Tangerang	3	30 H	Cipondoh	LS 6°10'56.55" BT 106°40'19.02"
Kab. Tangerang	4	35 B	Bojong Renged	LS 06 04' 26" BT 106 38' 70.1"
Kab. Tangerang	5	25 J	Mauk	LS 06 04' 85.5" BT 106 32' 44.9"
Kab. Tangerang	6	25 G	Sepatan	LS 06 07' 74.5" BT 106 35' 26.7"
Kab. Tangerang	7	JKT 25 K	Kronjo	LS 6° 3'56.19" BT 106°25'6.71"
Kab. Tangerang	8	25 A	Kresek	LS 6° 8'9.12" BT 106°23'12.99"
Kab. Tangerang	9	25 B	Balaraja Merak/Benda	LS 6° 9'2.62" BT 106°26'37.44"
Kab. Tangerang	10	25 H	Rajeg	LS 6° 7'42.10" BT 106°27'38.89"
Kab. Tangerang	11	25 C	Balaraja Kantor/UPTD	LS 06 11' 58.2" BT 106 27' 88.9"
Kab. Tangerang	12	-	Ciputat	LS 06 17' 32.8" BT 106 44' 03"
TOTAL	12			

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisadane, 202

Draw 1. Rainfall post location map

Source: Google Maps, 2022.

B. Measurement of discharge can be done both directly and indirectly. Direct discharge measurement is a measurement made using equipment in the form of a current meter, float, dye, etc. the discharge of the measurement results can be calculated as soon as the measurement is completed.

Indirect discharge measurement is a discharge measurement carried out using hydraulics formulas such as the Manning or Chezy formula. Measurements are carried

out by measuring the hydraulic parameters of the river, namely the cross-sectional area of the river, the wet circumference, and the slope of the energy line. The energy line is obtained from the former floods observed on the cliffs of the river. For water posts that are already equipped with a special pelskal the energy line can be read from the special pelskal.

The principle of using the current meter tool is to observe the number of revolutions of the pinwheel on the counter connected to the current meter tool within 30 seconds. This discharge measurement is carried out at 16 (fourteen) measurement post points, namely:

Table 2. Data on the location of the river flow discharge measurement post

No.	Sungai				Sta	Lokasi	Satuan Wilayah Sungai	Luas DAS (Km2)	Karakteristik Sungai		
	Kode	Nama Sungai Berdasarkan Orde Sungai							Panjang (Km)	Lebar (m)	Kelerengan
1	1.2.0.0.0	JALETRENG	LS 06 19' 42.7"	BT 106 40' 55"	02	Taman Kota BSD	Cidurian-Cisadane	36,8	4,9	7,5	Blm Ada AWLR
2	1.3.0.0.0	PEMB. KELAPA DUA	LS 06 14' 00.3"	BT 106°37'3.55"	03	Situ Kelapa Dua	Cidurian-Cisadane	20,4	2,9	7,0	Blm Ada AWLR
3	1.4.0.0.0	CIPASILIAN	LS 06 07' 41.03"	BT 106 26' 37.7"	02	Situ Cihuni	Cidurian-Cisadane	3,6	1,2	3,0	Blm Ada AWLR
4	2.1.0.0.0	CIMANCEURI	LS 06°18'06.0"	BT 106°30'29.02"	02	DS. Ranca Labuh	Cidurian-Cisadane	2.479,4	50,6	49,0	Blm Ada AWLR
5	4.1.0.0.0	ANGKE	LS 06 18' 56.2"	BT 106 42' 20.2"	02	Desa Ciater	Cidurian-Cisadane	540,0	45,0	12,0	Blm Ada AWLR
6	5.1.0.0.0	CIRARAB	LS 06° 9'11.93"	BT 106°34'55.28"	02	Perum Kutabumi	Cidurian-Cisadane	336,0	21,0	16,0	Blm Ada AWLR
7	7.1.0.0.0	S. PEMB. RAWA BESAR	LS 06°11'34.68"	BT 106°37'59.82"	03	Cikokol	Cidurian-Cisadane	1,20	0,40	3,0	Blm Ada AWLR
8	7.3.0.0.0	PEMB. SABI	LS 06 10' 14.5"	BT 106 36' 12.6"	03	Sangiang	Cidurian-Cisadane	71,2	8,9	8,0	Blm Ada AWLR
9	7.4.0.0.0	CIATER	LS 06°17'54.57"	BT 106°40'29.84"	03	BSD	Cidurian-Cisadane	3,6	1,2	3,0	Blm Ada AWLR
10		CIPAHEH	LS 6° 7'24.75"	BT 106°23'53.65"	03	Cipaeh	Cidurian-Cisadane	111,2	11,7	9,5	Blm Ada AWLR
11		KALI ASIN	LS 06° 7'16.59"	BT 106°36'7.65"	03	Kedaung	Cidurian-Cisadane	5,5	2,00	2,75	Blm Ada AWLR
12		PEMB. DADAP	LS 06° 5'27.31"	BT 106°41'32.60"	02	Kosambi	Cidurian-Cisadane	132,0	6,0	22,0	Blm Ada AWLR
13		PEMB. RAWA CIPONDOH	LS 6°11'18.18"	BT 106°40'34.97"	03	Poris	Cidurian-Cisadane	22,8	3,8	6,0	Blm Ada AWLR
14		CIPAYAHEUN	LS 6°15'54.72"	BT 106°27'29.89"	02	Cipayaheun	Cidurian-Cisadane	167,9	14,6	11,5	Blm Ada AWLR
15		CILELES	LS 06° 8'29.23"	BT 106°30'34.11"	02	Pasar Kemis	Cidurian-Cisadane	124,3	22,6	5,5	Blm Ada AWLR
16		S. TAHANG	LS 06° 4'28.35"	BT 106°40'26.13"	02	Salembaran	Cidurian-Cisadane	45,0	3,0	15,0	Blm Ada AWLR
TOTAL								4.100,8	199,7		

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisadane, 2022

Figure 2. Map of river flow discharge measurement post location

Source: Google Maps, 2022.

Table 3. Water sample data from 24 Location point of the river region

NO	LOKASI	GPS I	ALAMAT	GPS II	ALAMAT	KETERANGAN
1	S. Cimanceuri (Hulu)	E= 6°18'5.988" S=106°30'29.322"	Jl. Raya Kutruk Rancaiyuh, Ranca Iyuh Panongan Tangerang - Banten 15710			
2	S. Cimanceuri (Hilir)	S= 6°7'42.8088" E=106°27'35.7048"	Unnamed Road, Kemiri, Tangerang, Banten.	S = 06°7' 42,49164", E = 106° 27' 35,96076"	Jl. Ranca Labuh, Kemiri Tangerang- Banten	
3	S. Cipasilian	S= 6°7'41.07 E=106°26'38.1	Cirumpak, Krorjo, Tangerang - Banten 15550.			
4	S. Cidurian (Hulu)	L = -6.295288 B = 106.396548		S = 06°7' 40,44828", E = 106° 26' 36,80844"	Cirumpak Krorjo , Tangerang- Banten 15530	
5	S. Cidurian (Hilir)	S= 6°8'38.39028" E=106°23'16.98792"	Jl. Raya Kresak No. 5 Renged Kresak, Tangerang, Banten 42196 Indonesia.	S = 06°8' 38,62068", E = 106° 23' 17,21652"	Jl. Raya Kresak No. 05 Renged Kresak Tangerang- Banten 42198	
6	Sal. Induk Cidurian	S= 6°11'50.85276" E=106°26'55.0806"	Tobat, Balaraja, Tangerang, Banten.			
7	S. Cirarab (Hulu)	S= 6°11'50.85276" E=106°26'55.0806"	Jl. Raya Cung No. 88 Mekar Jaya, Panongan Tangerang - Banten 15710			
8	S. Cirarab (Hilir)			S = 06°5' 40,77024", E = 106° 35' 7,41624"	Jl. Raya Pakuhaji No. 84 Kayu Agung Sepatan Tangerang 15529	
9	Sal. Pemb. Kelapa Dua	S=6°14'0.456", E = 106°37'3.8064"	Jl. Kelapa Dua Raya No. 33-93 Kelapa Dua Tangerang- Banten 15810	S = 06°14' 0,02976", E = 106° 37' 4,2474"	Jl. Raya danau kelapa dua Kota Tangerang- Banten 15810	
10	S. Sabi (Hulu)	S=6°13'6.9384", E = 106°35'35.8944"	Jl. Danau Sentani Kota Tangerang - Banten 15810	S = 06° 13,647292", E = 106° 35,36,00744"	Jl. Empu Tantular Gandesari, Jatiluwung Kota Tangerang Banten 15810	
11	S. Sabi (Hilir)	S=6°10'15.006", E = 106°38'12.3352"	Jl. Raya Mauk No. 3 Peruk Kota Tangerang - Banten	S = 06° 10'14,62476", E = 106° 38' 12,54528"	Jl. Moch Toha Km. 2 Bugel, Karawaci Peruk Tangerang - Banten 15132	
12	Sal. Pemb. Jalitreg	S = 06° 10,471", E = 106° 38,468"		S = 06° 9'13,02192", E = 106° 38' 28,0544"	Jl.	
13	S. Cisdane (Intake PDAM)	S=6°19'56.5536", E = 106°39'26.154"	Jl. Momonggor, Kranggan Setu, Kota Tangerang Selatan, Banten 15312	S = 06°18' 44,29116", E = 106° 39' 30,13884"	Jl. Sidamank No. Kav. 9 Cilenggang Serpong Kota Tangsel 15310	
14	S. Cisdane (Jemb. Robinson)	S=6°10'48.6284", E = 106°37'44.3172"	Jl. Kali Pasir Indah No. 50 - 59 Sukasari, Kec. Tangerang, Banten 15118 Indonesia	S = 06°10' 48,63252", E = 106° 37' 44,59224"	Jl. Kalipasis Indah No. 59 Sukatani Kec. Tangerang Kota Tangerang 15118 Banten	
15	S. Cisdane (Jemb. Kali Baru)	S=6°34'2.876", E = 106°37'57.972"	Jl. Raya Kali Baru No. 168 Kalibaru, Pakuhaji, Tangerang 15570	S = 06°3' 42,92568", E = 106° 38' 1,13884"	Jl. Kalibaru -1 Tanjung Burung Teluknaga Tangerang	
16	Sal. Induk Timur	S = 06° 07,50.67", E = 106° 64,11.60"	Kp. Melayu Barat Teluknaga - Tangerang	S = 06° 07,50.67", E = 106° 38' 28,0544"	Jl. Ingsi Katang Amyar, Neglasari Tangerang- Banten	
17	Sal. Induk Barat	S=6°7'47.3652", E = 106°31'36.1848"	Jl. Raya Ps. Mauk- Rajeg, Mekarsari Tangerang - Banten 15540	S = 06° 7'49,66032", E = 106° 31' 35,39064"	Jl. Pasar Kemis, Sukatani Rajeg, Tangerang- Banten	
18	Sal. Cisdane Barat Laut	S=6°52.3423", E = 106°32'38.7852"	Jl. Raya Mauk, Jatwirangin Mauk, Tangerang, Banten 15330	S = 06° 5' 3,75684", E = 106° 32' 36,34008"	Jl. Jati Tarjakan, Jatwirangin Mauk, Tangerang - Banten 15330	
19	S. Angke (Hulu)	S = 06° 13,20.5", E = 106° 41,45.7"	Kel. Pondok Jagung Timur Kec. Serpong Utara	S = 06°18' 56,8116", E = 106° 42' 19,35504"		
20	S. Angke (Hilir)	S = 06° 13,22.4", E = 106° 41,46.9"	Kel. Sudimara Pinang Kec. Pinang	S = 06°13' 21,08784", E = 106° 41' 44,74572"	Jl. Anggrek jingga II, Rw. Buntu, Serpong - Kota Tangerang Selatan Banten 15310	
21	S. Ciater	S=6°17.54.186", E = 106°40'29.9568"	Jl. Hebras No. 50 Serpong Kota Tangerang Selatan Banten 15310	S = 06°13' 21,08784", E = 106° 41' 44,74572"		
22	Situ Cipondoh	S=6°19'57.27", E = 106°67'71.63"	Jl. Hasyim Asnari Cipondoh Kota Tangerang 15148	S=6°17'53,9232", E = 106°40'29,35524"		
23	Situ Garukgak	S=6°16'82.13", E = 106°49'00.01"	Sindang Jaya, Tangerang- Banten	S=6°7'24,59424", E = 106°24'6,3306"	unnamed Road Talok, Kresak Tangerang- Banten 15620	
24	Rawa Pondok	S=6°17.02.80", E = 106°52'39.75"	Kp. Pondok SukaHarja, SindangJaya, Tangerang, Banten	S=6°10'14,88876", E = 106°31'24,79188"	Jl. Sindang Rawa Kp. Pondok Sindang Jaya Pasar Kemis Tangerang 15560	

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisdane, 2022

Figure 3. River basin location map

Source: Google Maps, 2022.

- C. The recording of water level height is in the hydrological post that records the water level in a particular river. Recording the height of the water level can be done in two ways / tools with automatic and manual tools. The data was obtained from the reading of the AWLR graph which is the result of recording the level of river water level in a certain time in the form of a hydrography which shows the height of the river water level in a certain time in the form of a hydrograph which shows the height of the water level /TMA (meters) and time (hours). Meanwhile, manual recording of water level height is done by observing the high level of water level with peilschale board. This recording is carried out at 5 (five) observation points of water level height.

Table 4. Water level high post location

No.	Nama Sungai Berdasarkan Orde Sungai			Sta	Lokasi	Satuan Wilayah Sungai
1	AWLR SERPONG	LS 6°18'41.93"	BT 106°39'29.71"		Desa Cisauk Serpong	Cidurian-Cisadane
2	AWLR ANGKE	LS 6°18'57.43"	BT 106°42'19.52"		Ciater BSD	Cidurian-Cisadane
3	BDG RANCA SUMUR	LS 6°17'43.80"	BT 106°23'47.35"		Cidurian	Cidurian-Cisadane
4	POS AWLR Batu Beulah	LS 6°23'7.16"	BT 106°38'46.82"		Batu Beulah Cisadane Hulu	Cidurian-Cisadane
5	BDG GARUKGAK	LS 6° 7'23.94"	BT 106°24'6.12"		Desa Cipaeh	Cidurian-Cisadane
TOTAL						

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisadane, 2022

Figure 4. Water level high post location map

Source: Google Maps, 2022.

- D. Flood monitoring is carried out 4 months a year where in that month it is estimated that the rainy season. Flood monitoring is carried out in January, February, November and December.

Table 5. Location of flood monitoring posts on 4 posts

No.	Nama Sungai Berdasarkan Orde Sungai			Lokasi	Satuan Wilayah Sungai
			Sta tus		
1	BDG PASAR BARU	LS 6° 9'37.02"	BT 106°37'38.64"	Kelurahan Koang Jaya	Cidurian-Cisadane
2	BDG RANCA SUMUR	LS 6°17'43.80"	BT 106°23'47.35"	Cidurian	Cidurian-Cisadane
3	BDG CIPUTAT	LS 6°17'32.70"	BT 106°44'2.71"	Sawah Lama	Cidurian-Cisadane
4	BDG SARAKAN	LS 6° 6'33.36"	BT 106°33'23.03"	Sarakan	Cidurian-Cisadane
TOTAL					

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisadane, 2022

Figure 5. Location map of flood monitoring posts on 4 posts

Source: Google Maps, 2022.

- E. In this benchmark, a water meter is recorded from each water user who uses water in the work area in the cisadane river flow where surface water users are required to record daily water use which will be accumulated by water meter registrars in the form of monthly reports of water use which will be submitted to tax collectors in this case carried out by BAPENDA (Regional Revenue Agency of Banten Province).

The use of surface water in Banten Province which is included in the cisadane watershed working area amounts to 95 (ninety-five) surface water users, of which 80 (eighty) consists of companies and 15 (fifteen) consists of PDAMs along with a table of surface water users:

Figure 6. Map of the company's water meter recording location Tangerang City

Source: Google Maps, 2022

Figure 7. Map of the company's water meter recording location south tangerang city

Source: Google Maps, 2022

The survey and investigation of the hydrological building post functioned to find out the condition of the hydrological post at that time whether there was heavy, light damage or the condition of the equipment and buildings was in good condition.

Figure 8. Location map of activities survey and investigation of hydrological building posts

Source: Google Maps, 2022

LITERATURE STUDIES

Based on the search for articles in the Scopus database using the Boolean operator by filling in the search box as follows: TITLE-ABS-KEY (Performance AND "Watershed Management") AND (EXCLUDE (PUBYEAR, 2022)) AND (LIMIT-TO (LANGUAGE, "English")) AND (LIMIT-TO (DOCTYPE, "ar")), the results were found. The 299 previous studies that were then processed with the VOSviewer application were presented in the figure overlay visualization below.

Figure 9. Overlay visualization of performance and watershed management article

Source: Processed from VOSviewer app, 2022

Previous researchers contained in the scopus database discussed more related public participation in solving complex water problems and maintaining the health of rivers and lakes in China (Wu et al., 2020), Assessment of the hydrological performance of regulated strategies for flood mitigation in Brazil (Gomes Calixto et al., 2020), Comparing complexity in tata watershed management in California (Ulibarri & Garcia, 2020), Constraints and committee contributions in watershed management in Brazil (de Lima Trindade & Scheibe, 2019), Performance of national maps of watershed integrity on the watershed scale (Kuhn et al., 2018), Improving the effectiveness of collaborative tata management regimes dar i watershed partnerships (Biddle, 2017), A collaborative approach to the calibration of river water quality models (von Stackelberg & Neilson, 2014), Optimizing watershed management with coordinated operation of storage facilities (Anghileri et al., 2013) and Evaluation of licensing programs to regulate surface water intake (An & Eheart, 2006). Thus, based on the results of previous research searches, no one has specifically discussed the performance of water resource information systems in watersheds (das).

Performance has been a major discourse in public administration since reinventing government was introduced by Osborn and Gaebler (Osborne & Gaebler, 1993). The performance of local governments is the performance of local government organizations or agencies. Therefore, the definition of organizational performance can be used as a basis for formulating the performance of government organizations. Organizational performance describes how far an organization has achieved results after comparison with previous performance, with other organizations and to how far it has achieved the goals and targets that have been set (Muhammad, 2008). (THEORY 1) The Government Accounting Standard Board (GASB) in (Bernstein, 2001) divides performance measurements into three categories of indicators, namely:

- 1). Indicators of measuring service efforts (how resources are used to carry out various programs or services that are diverse)
- 2). Indicators of service accomplishment measurement (achievements of a particular program)
- 3). Indicators that link efforts to accomplishments

Meanwhile, according to John Miner (Sudarmanto, 2009: 11-12) put forward four dimensions that can be used as indicators in assessing organizational performance, namely:

- 1). Quality: error rate, damage, meticulousness.
- 2). Quantity: the amount of work produced.
- 3). Use of time in work: absenteeism rate, delay, effective working time/lost working hours.
- 4). Cooperation with others in work.

(OR THEORY 3) The performance theory used in this researches the Balanced Scorecard. According to Niven, the Balanced Scorecard is a set of quantitatively selected indicators that are selectively derived from the company's strategy (Niven, 2003). BSC results are chosen as a tool for leaders to communicate to employees and external stakeholders regarding outcomes and performance drivers that help the organization achieve its mission and strategic objectives.

The Balanced Scorecard aims to measure a company's performance from four perspectives: finance, customer, internal process, learning and growth (learning)." Therefore, these four perspectives need to be considered in developing visions and strategies (Kaplan & Norton, 2000). Regarding the Balanced Scorecard in the public sector, according to Niven, the adaptation of the Balanced Scorecard in the public sector has changed from the original version which looks as follows:

- a) The mission has moved to the top of the Balanced Scorecard.
- b) The strategy remains central to the Balanced Scorecard.
- c) The customer/stakeholder perspective replaces the financial perspective.
- d) Since there is no Balanced Scorecard without a financial perspective, the financial perspective remains, but is positioned as a support in terms of learning and growth.
- e) Identify internal processes that increase customer value.
- f) The perspective of learning and growth continues to be the basis of the Balanced Scorecard (Niven, 2003).

Figure 10. Balanced scorecard perspectives in public sector organizations

Source: Niven, 2003

RESEARCH METHODS

1. Qualitative

The method in this study uses descriptive qualitative. Descriptive research is a study that describes what happens when conducting research. This study seeks to describe, record, analyze and interpret the conditions that occur at the research site and see the relationship between dimensions. Data analysis techniques in qualitative research according to Creswell are carried out through the following steps:

- 1). Processing and preparing data for analysis
- 2). Read the entire data
- 3). Analyze in more detail by coding the data
- 4). apply the coding process to describe the settings, those categories and themes to be analyzed
- 5). Show how these descriptions and themes will be presented back in a qualitative narrative/report. (Creswell, 2014)

2. Or Quantitative

The research method used is a quantitative research method with a survey research design. Quantitative research methods are methods to test certain theories by examining the relationship between variables. These variables are measured usually by research instruments so that data consisting of numbers can be analyzed based on statistical procedures (Creswell, 2014). This study uses a survey research design with the aim of presenting a quantitative description or numerical description of the tendencies, attitudes, or opinions of a particular population by examining a sample of that population.

DISCUSSION

The purpose of this performance activity is to be able to produce an inventory survey of hydrological post buildings into report materials, so that they can be immediately followed up for the maintenance of hydrological post buildings which consist of water level height observation posts, discharge measurement posts and rainfall posts. Maintenance of hydrological facilities and infrastructure is an activity that is needed for the continuity of rainfall activities, discharge measurement, sample measurement and flood monitoring so that access to activity location points is easily reached, so that the results of activities in performance can be carried out accurately. Maintenance of hydrological facilities and infrastructure is carried out periodically, namely for 4 (four) periods in 1 (one) year. This is done so that performance can run well, where access to the activity location point is easily accessible by the implementing officers of activities in the field in addition to getting maximum discharge measurement results in particular. The collection and processing of hydrological data in the performance targets of the implementation of the benchmark for the collection and processing of hydrological data there are 12 (twelve) rainfall data collection points, 16 (sixteen)

discharge measurement points, 5 (five) water level height recording points and 24 (twenty-four) sampling points.

- A. The implementation of rainfall data collection is carried out by rainfall data collection officers in each month. Daily rainfall data is submitted by BMKG officers who record daily rainfall data taken from 12 (twelve) rainfall posts

Table 6. Rainfall data for the period 5 years and below New market weir rainfall post

JUMLAH CURAH HUJAN BULANAN (mm)

Nama Pos	PASAR BARU		
Nomor Pos	301	Elevasi	
No.di Database		Tipe alat	MANUAL
Lintang Selatan	06.09.563'	Pemilik	BMG
Bujur Timur	106.37.615'	Pengamat	M sukarman
		Desa	MEKARSARI
		Kecamatan	TANGERANG
		Kabupaten	TANGERANG

Tahun	Jan	Peb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Ags	Sep	Okt	Nop	Des	Tahunan	
													Total (mm/thn)	R ₂₄ (mm)
2017	211	273	176	92	79	82	124	18	23	25	34	173	1.310,00	
2018	98	384	56	273	50	94	-	-	5	19	50	26	1.055,00	
2019	211	273	176	92	79	82	-	-	-	-	34	54	1.001,00	
2020	473	485	88	79	45	47	30	14	53	46	6,5	65	1.431,50	1
2021	60	196,2	45	56	32	-	17	20	31	35	34	-	526,20	
Max	473,0	485,0	176,0	273,0	79,0	94,0	124,0	20,0	53,0	46,0	50,0	173,0	1.431,50	
Rerata	210,6	322,2	108,2	118,4	57,0	61,0	34,2	10,4	22,4	25,0	31,7	63,6	1.064,74	
Min	60,0	196,2	45,0	56,0	32,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	0,0	6,5	0,0	526,20	

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisadane, 2022

The results of this daily rainfall recording report are submitted by the rainfall data collection officer every month, which is then submitted to the rainfall data processing officer. Rainfall data processing officers process the data by importing the rainfall data to a computer for further analysis so as to produce a monthly rainfall graph. BMKG rainfall recording officers use telemetry tools as a tool to measure rainfall.

B. Measurement of river water discharge is carried out at 16 (enam belas) points scattered in the cisadane watershed work area where the measurement is carried out by 3 (three) officers where 2 (two) people measure the width of the river which 1 (one) person is drooling using a current meter tool and there are other officers who document the recording and measurement of discharge and record each implementation carried out n in several stages including:

- 1) Preparation of the tool
- 2) Blangko debit measurement

The measurement of discharge in the field is carried out when all stages have been prepared where the stages are carried out through discharge measurement activities in the field.

The method used in the implementation of river flow discharge measurement here uses 2 (two) measurement methods, namely the Merawas method and the Bridge Side method. The measurement of discharge by means of merawas is the measuring officer directly entering the body of water, and the measurement of discharge from the side of the bridge is a measurement made from the side of the bridge downstream of the flow and preferably the bridge used does not have pillars. The equipment used is a bridge crane, sounding reel, tagline, and 1 set of current meter + ballast whose weight depends on the flow speed.

At this stage, several steps of work are needed before carrying out measurements including:

a. River width measurement

After the river location point is found, a measurement of the width of the river is carried out first using a meter which is then recorded directly to the measurement blangko. It is necessary in the division of measurement points so that the measurement of the discharge is evenly distributed.

b. Measurement of water temperature in rivers

Furthermore, the temperature of local river water is measured using a water temperature measuring device, this is very important to support the accuracy of the data in making a discharge calculation report and field measurement results which will be in the form of a report.

c. Division of discharge measurement points

After it is known that the width of the river has been measured at the stage of measuring the width of the river, the division of measurement points is carried out so that the

measurement of the discharge is flat and balanced. The division of the measuring points must correspond to the width of the local river.

d. Discharge measurement stage

This step is a continuation of the previous step, namely the determination of measurement points. After obtaining the measurement point, then the discharge measurement activity begins at the first and subsequent points. In the measurement of discharge, it must be known the depth of the river that has been measured first. Discharge measurement is also carried out with supporting means such as bridges, boats, mines (if the current state of the river is large) and using cranes, according to the state of the local river location.

e. Debit calculation

After the next performance activity from the officer, namely the measurements carried out and recorded the speed flow, the calculation of debit data must be carried out which will later be known the average river discharge and the overall river discharge.

f. Report generation

Measurements in the field are completed, so a report on the results of debit measurements is carried out. The data that has been recorded and calculated on the debit measurement record, then inputted in the form of a computer format to be used as material for monthly reports of debit measurement results.

The following is one of the data from measuring the discharge of river flows in the field that has been inputted into the computerization. One of the data that has been made in the past 5 years is:

Table 7. Data on the results of measuring river flow discharge for a period of 5 years and below sabi waster river discharge measurement post

Tahun	NAMA BULAN												DEBIT MAXIMUM
	JANUARI	PEBRUARI	MARET	APRIL	MEI	JUNI	JULI	AGUSTUS	SEPTEMBER	OKTOBER	NOPEMBER	DESEMBER	
2017	4,288	5,066	3,848	6,095	5,499	4,221	1,446	1,328	1,811	1,628	1,853	1,924	6,095
2018	6,168	5,238	3,769	4,002	2,051	1,725	1,328	1,214	1,111	1,559	1,791	5,752	6,168
2019	6,242	5,042	5,748	4,128	2,181	1,837	1,734	1,147	0,715	2,542	3,485	5,516	6,242
2020	3,520	9,063	3,384			2,496							9,063
2021	12,466	30,453	7,077	4,992	3,372	1,696	1,508	1,131	6,093	4,092	5,489	7,343	30,453

Keterangan : - Perbedaan hasil debit dikarenakan adanya pergantian titik Lokasi Pos Pengukuran Debit Aliran Sungai.
 - Sungai Pembuang Sabi tahun 2011 tidak ada data dikarenakan belum ada kegiatan ukur debit pada lokasi tersebut.

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisadane, 2022

Water level tightening is a hydrological post that records the water level in a certain river, data is obtained from the AWLR graph reading which is the result of recording the river water level in a certain time in the form of a hydrography that shows the height of the water level / TMA (meters) and time (hours). The data that has been processed / analyzed produces data on the average water level (TMA), this data is data obtained from the AWLR post, AWLL Post and the Ordinary Water Suspect Post (peiscal reading). This AWLR/AWLL and PDAB equipment is installed at an observation post that places it in a river/bending and is monitored and observed for 3 (three) times a day. The result of recording the AWLR / AWLL tool is in the form of a graph that depicts the relationship of time and water level height, from the graph of the recording results, it is then analyzed to find the average water level height.

The following is one of the data that has been inputted into computerization, the data created is one of the data from the Cisauk TMA post located in Serpong, South Tangerang City in the past 10 years, is:

Table 8. Data on the results of recording water levels Period 10 years and below serpong water level post

Tahun	Jan	Feb	Mar	Apr	Mei	Jun	Jul	Ags	Sep	Okt	Nop	Des	Tahunan	
													(m ³ /det)	(mm)
2008	92,893	104,989	114,634	110,990	69,784	44,892	19,046	31,881	56,992	103,853	128,413	66,405	78,731	1764,468
2009	101,984	124,095	65,211	64,710	111,574	67,654	29,109	17,439	24,807	58,313	121,985	76,941	71,985	1608,875
2010	82,077	116,064	111,069	31,690	77,251	89,339	66,213	92,314	127,561	100,907	101,277	69,936	88,808	1984,871
2011	59,252	33,446	32,890	59,743	75,862	59,805	64,427	22,470	19,270	30,848	102,510	63,211	51,978	1161,710
2012	101,883	123,852	46,960	108,759	65,139	31,363	35,843	9,388	23,181	155,495	161,622	114,392	81,490	1826,295
2013	146,715	80,996	96,894	103,021	tad	tad	tad	tad	tad	tad	tad	tad	tad	tad
2014	280,293	189,811	84,200	122,163	102,420	52,181	60,243	81,910	31,863	28,429	82,031	0,000	92,962	2083,402
2019	68,739	207,908	56,917	113,842	114,607	41,936	3,313	12,943	12,523	70,413	100,121	135,565	78,236	1753,364
2020	173,159	122,450	186,724	119,906	224,345	161,325	68,472	50,660	100,309	177,821	106,590	107,707	133,289	2987,185
2021	98,209	167,287	60,941	100,152	159,211	tad	46,629	59,977	91,030	74,679	92,440	95,820	tad	tad
Max	280,293	207,908	186,724	151,864	224,345	161,325	86,504	94,592	127,561	177,821	161,622	152,406	133,289	2987,185
Rerata	109,841	124,108	84,837	95,851	96,471	62,880	46,347	39,978	48,900	76,652	94,640	82,198	79,647	1782,100
Min	40,863	33,446	32,890	31,690	43,620	29,064	3,313	8,837	7,744	9,631	38,300	0,000	47,114	1053,008

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisadane, 2022

If there is damage to the AWLR / AWLL tool, then manually observe the water level (ordinary water guessing post) by reading the pelischal directly. The recording time and the implementation officer of the Post are:

1. Manual water guessing posts (pelischaals) are measured and recorded by the postkeepers every day at 06:00, 12:00, and 18:00 local time.
2. The automatic water level recorder (AWLR) post is taken and replaced with graph paper by the post guard according to the type of tool installed (every day, weekly or every three months).
3. The automatic water level logger (AWLL) post is downloaded (downloaded) digital data by the hydrological management officer every 2 or 3 months.

Sampling was carried out at 24 (twenty-four) location points spread across 3 work areas, namely Tangerang City, Tangerang Regency, and South Tangerang where river water sampling was carried out to facilitate the implementation of activities in the performance of officers in the field. Water sampling is carried out by officers who conduct PH tests in the field using a PH meter tool. Water sampling is carried out regularly every month, the mechanism for taking water samples includes:

1. Sampling
2. Transportation
3. Laboratory Testing
4. Reporting of results and assessments

The management of surface water use data on this benchmark is carried out by water meter recording officers in the administrative performance area in Tangerang City, Tangerang Regency and South Tangerang in the Banten Province area, this is done for the purpose of collecting water taxes carried out by BAPENDA. In the performance carried out with limited Human Resources, reliable personnel are still needed in supporting the implementation of this water utilization activity in order to further increase regional income in the Banten Province area. From the performance that has been running, the preparation of quarterly evaluations of officers is obliged to evaluate the results of work in carrying out work which is a means of periodic performance monitoring based on the realization of indicators in performance progress.

The following is one of the water quality data that has been input into computerization, the data presented is water quality data for downstream angke rivers in 2019, are:

Table 9. Water quality data 2019 water quality of downstream angke river

NO	PARAMETER	SATUAN	BAKU MUTU KELAS II	BULAN												JLH DATA	NILAI			BAKU MUTU KELAS II	SKOR			
				JAN	FEB	MRT	APRIL	MEI	JUNI	JULI	AGUST	SEPT	OKT	NOV	DES		MIN	MAX	RATA2		MIN	MAX	RATA2	TOTAL
				HASIL UJI																				
PARAMETER																								
1	Temperatur	°C	27 - 32,5	27,1	27,2	31,1	28,0	27,9	27,9	27,8	28,7	26,0	27,9	27,1	26,6	12	12	31,1	26,5615	27 - 32,5	0,00	-2,00	0,00	-2,00
2	Daya Hantar Listrik	umhos	2250	210,0	203,1	178,5	344,2	395,0	395,0	286,8	304,1	360,9	320,4	136,1	138,2	12	136,1	395,02	272,6850	2250	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
3	kekeruhan /Turbidity	Ntu	25	57	40	95	34	4	4	11	9	4	5	11	27	12	4	94,6	25,0500	25	0,00	-2,00	-6,00	-8,00
4	Total Dissolved Solid (TDS)	mg/l	1000	130	108	43	183	212	212	152	167	192	172	72	73	12	43	212	143,0500	1000	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
5	Total Suspended Solid (TSS)	mg/l	50	60	54,0	54,0	52,0	8,0	8,0	29,0	54,0	10,0	38,0	54,0	54,0	12	8	60	39,5833	50	0,00	-2,00	0,00	-2,00
6	Warna	PCo	50	15,456	6,013	64,0	30,0	15,0	15,0	24,0	83,0	81,0	15,0	23,0	42,0	12	6,013	83	34,4558	50	0,00	-2,00	0,00	-2,00
7	Sedimen			55				16	16	35	55	4	106	76	43	12								
KIMIA																								
8	pH	-	6 - 9	7,19	7,26	7,38	7,26	7,67	7,67	7,37	8,26	7,30	7,54	7,39	7,42	12	7,19	8,26	7,4758	6 - 9	-4,00	-4,00	-12,00	-20,00
9	Oksigen Terlarut (DO)	mg/l	4	6,158	5,066	7,052	7,350	3,178	3,178	5,165	5,960	0	6,754	6,158	6,754	12	0	7,35	5,2311	4	0,00	-4,00	-12,00	-16,00
10	COD	mg/l	25	7,936	23,520	15,680	39,200	47,040	47,040	39,200	39,200	54,880	23,808	23,673	15,680	12	7,936	54,88	31,4048	25	0,00	-4,00	-12,00	-16,00
11	BOD	mg/l	3	1,183	1,193	1,987	1,589	7,948	7,948	1,987	1,391	5,762	1,689	1,183	1,689	12	1,183	7,948	2,9624	3	0,00	-4,00	0,00	-4,00
12	Nilai Permanganat (KMnO4)	mg/l	10	3,476	6,952	6,636	8,216	9,164	9,164	5,056	6,636	10,112	6,636	6,636	9,796	12	3,476	10,112	7,3733	10	0,00	-4,00	0,00	-4,00
13	Mesadahan Total	mg/l	300	112	128	104	248	232	232	76	92	260	100	116	120	12	76	260	151,6667	300	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
14	Clorida (Cl)	mg/l	600	3,498	7,508	6,507	11,012	20,493	20,493	11,012	7,508	23,026	9,447	9,511	9,010	12	3,498	23,026	11,5854	600	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
15	Calسيوم (Ca)	mg/l	200	32,0	19,2	17,6	67,2	38,8	38,8	17,6	19,0	80	17,6	28,8	12,8	12	12,8	80	32,4500	200	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
16	Magnesium (Mg)	mg/l	150	7,776	19,44	150	19,44	14,58	14,58	7,776	10,692	22,356	13,608	10,692	21,384	12	7,776	150	26,0270	150	0,00	-4,00	0,00	-4,00
17	Besi (Fe)	mg/l	0,3	0,42	0,82	0,3	0,68	0,83	0,83	0,19	0,42	0,65	0,83	0,65	0,65	12	0,19	0,83	0,6058	0,3	0,00	-4,00	-12,00	-16,00
18	Timbal (Pb)	mg/l	0,03	0,39	0,59	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,07	0,21	0,26	0,25	0,07	0,23	0,37	12	0,07	0,21	0,3708	0,03	-4,00	-4,00	-12,00	-20,00
19	Tembaga (Cu)	mg/l	0,02	0,12	0,20	0,50	0,50	0,07	0,07	0,26	1,17	1,15	0,07	1,15	1,15	12	0,07	1,17	0,5342	0,02	-4,00	-4,00	-12,00	-20,00
20	Zeng (Zn)	mg/l	0,05	1,69	1,22	1,87	0,89	0,91	0,91	0,43	0,89	0,87	0,91	0,15	1,22	12	0,15	1,87	0,9967	0,05	-4,00	-4,00	-12,00	-20,00
21	Kromium Total (Cr)	mg/l	0,05	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0,0000	0,05	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
22	Cadmium (Cd)	mg/l	0,01	0,031	0,061	0,320	0,05	0,07	0,07	0,08	0,041	0,075	0,07	0,038	0,027	12	0,027	0,32	0,0771	0,01	-4,00	-4,00	-12,00	-20,00
23	Fenol	mg/l	0,001	0,0184	0,0425	0,0251	0,0340	0,0378	0,0378	0,0456	0,0184	0,0289	0,0378	0,0456	0,0456	12	0,0184	0,0456	0,0348	0,001	-4,00	-4,00	-12,00	-20,00
24	Minyak dan Lemak	mg/l	1	0,014	0,210	0,010	0,023	0,051	0,051	0,016	0,024	0,063	0,024	0,035	0,068	12	0,01	0,21	0,0491	1	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
25	Nitrat (NO3-N)	mg/l	10	0,411	13,021	0,385	24,018	3,060	3,060	29,936	7,765	7,763	3,060	7,763	7,763	12	0,385	29,936	9,0004	10	0,00	-4,00	0,00	-4,00
26	Nitrit (NO2-N)	mg/l	0,05	0,010	0,004	0,080	0,029	0,033	0,033	0,079	0,001	0,020	0,033	0,020	0,020	12	0,001	0,08	0,0302	0,05	0,00	-4,00	0,00	-4,00
27	Sulfat (SO4)	mg/l	400	0,368	0,370	0,372	0,372	0,318	0,318	0,119	23,509	23,507	0,318	23,507	23,507	12	0,119	23,509	8,0488	400	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
28	Amonia	mg/l	0,02	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	0	12	0	0	0,0000	0,02	0,00	0,00	0,00	0,00
29	Phospat (PO4)	mg/l	0,02	13,747	5,774	4,871	0,121	0,471	0,471	0,291	0,544	0,542	0,471	0,542	0,070	12	0,07	13,747	2,3263	0,02	-4,00	-4,00	-12,00	-20,00
BAKTERIOLOGI																								
1	Total Coli	Angka MPN/100ml	5000	3000	11000	27000	22000	48000	48000	11000	27000	27000	17000	27000	27000	12	3000	48000	24583	5000	0,00	-6,00	-18,00	-24,00
2	E Coliform	Angka MPN/100ml	1000	1000	2000	11000	8000	16000	16000	2000	8000	8000	7000	11000	15000	12	1000	16000	8750	1000	-6,00	-6,00	-18,00	-30,00

Source: Balai Besar Ciliwung-Cisadane, 2022

CONCLUSION

The implementation of activities in the management of the water resources information system of the cisadane watershed, Banten Province is an activity that has been carried out regularly for the needs of water resources that are needed by the community, including for clean water needs, especially PDAMs, therefore the performance of monitoring officers and recording water levels must be more optimal in any conditions so that it has an impact on the interests and the needs of the water user community. Activities that contain hydrological elements must be carried out accurately, considering that the data is widely used for all public interests, especially in planning a water building, bridges and planning a residential area close to the river channel, it must be known data on river surface water level and rainfall data on local areas first, which is to avoid the effects of flood-prone areas that are possible in the area. Good performance plays an important role in helping to carry out the main tasks of work and activities that take place in an effort to increase Regional Income Tax.

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